

Making sense of marine management – The ten-tenets revisited

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ABSTRACT

The so-called ten-tenets were proposed over a decade ago to indicate actions to achieve sustainable and successful marine management. These indicated that marine management actions should be *Ecologically sustainable, Technologically feasible, Economically viable, Socially tolerable/desirable, Legally defensible, Administratively achievable, Politically expedient, Ethically defensible/morally correct, Culturally inclusive* and *Effectively communicable*. These concepts are revisited here to show a continuum from an Ecosystem-Based Approach (EBA, setting the priorities and policies), to Ecosystem-Based Management (EBM, operationalising the approach by management and governance) and then using tools, including technological and economic instruments, now termed Ecosystem-Based Technical Measures (EBTM). This shows the way the tenets overlap while the underlying definitions still hold for holistic marine management and are valuable in prioritising marine management actions. We emphasise that the tenets for the overarching ecological and communication aspects should be weighted differently but that taken together all other tenets would be weighted equally although they could have a weighting depending on their user. For example, the economic tenet may be weighted highly in economically-challenging times and the cultural tenet in areas with indigenous peoples.

1. Introduction

The so-called ten-tenets of successful and sustainable marine management (Table 1) were first proposed in *Marine Pollution Bulletin* over a decade ago (Elliott, 2013) and since then they have been included and cited in many projects, papers and chapters. Given developments since that time, it is appropriate to revisit the concepts within the main aim of marine management ‘to protect and maintain the ecological structure and functioning to create ecosystem services from which we gain societal goods and benefits after inputting human capital and complementary assets’ (Elliott and Kennish, 2024). Successful marine management would then achieve the vision of ‘clean, healthy, safe, productive, biologically diverse marine and coastal environments, managed to meet the long-term needs of people and nature’.¹ Both of these quotations reinforce balancing nature and society as emphasised by the tenets.

Prior to developing the tenets, the three pillars of sustainability (ecology, economy and society) were commonly cited (e.g. Purvis et al., 2019; Montefalcone et al., 2025). Each of these pillars has its own information and constraints but they have not been integrated. Furthermore, they do not cover all aspects of marine management and are

insufficient given that ‘society’ includes many facets and governance was not explicit in any of the three. This led to the development, through several iterations, to the ten-tenets (Elliott, 2013). Recent advances have analysed how their success can be measured, again emphasising the need for a re-evaluation (Elliott et al., 2025). The ten-tenets concept is partly analogous to, but was separately derived from, the business-orientated PESTLE approach in which a business operates in a Political, Economic, Social, Technical and Legal Environment (Aguilar, 1967; IEC/ISO, 2019), although this omits the natural environmental and ecological aspects.

As in all scientific fields, it is important to always make sure the terms are defined and understood, that they can respond to changing circumstances and they occur within a well-defined framework. The tenet topic is the fundamental feature and then with an adjective leading to its accompanying adverb aims to help to achieve successful and sustainable management (the when, where, how, why of marine management). These then can be interrogated to determine who is doing public and private management (e.g. Elliott et al., 2025).

This paper advocates a continuum from an approach to an operationalisation of that approach to the tools and methods for that

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¹ Scotland’s vision on marine management: <https://marine.gov.scot/sma/assessment-theme/managing-human-activities-have-impact-scotlands-seas>.

Table 1
The ten-tenets and their meaning, modified and updated from Elliott (2013).

Tenet	Meaning – achieving the tenet should ensure that
1- Ecologically sustainable human pressures (e.g. from a development or activity) should not impact on ecosystem features and functioning, and both fundamental and final ecosystem services in the natural domain, should be preserved and safeguarded, where needed, by management responses
2- Technologically feasible methods, techniques and equipment are available and used for protecting natural ecosystems, society and infrastructure
3- Economically viable the methods for sustainable environmental management should be affordable; a cost-benefit assessment of management measures will indicate financial viability and sustainability
4- Legally permissible there are regional, national or international agreements and/or statutes which will enable and/or force management measures to be performed and upheld to protect the environment; horizontal links and vertical hierarchies of legal instruments will be accommodated
5- Administratively achievable statutory bodies (such as governmental departments, environmental protection and conservation bodies) are in place and functioning to enable successful and sustainable management; marine users are administered to protect the environment; horizontal links and vertical hierarchies of statutory management are accommodated and link to the business administration by other users
6- Socially desirable/tolerable society regards the development or activity and their environmental management as necessary, or the underlying pressures and demands are at least understood, and the developments are tolerated by society; individual and societal behaviour are recognised and included in management; societal goods and benefits are satisfied or at least their lack is tolerated
7- Politically expedient a development or activity and management approaches and philosophies are consistent with the prevailing political climate and have the support of political leaders; manifesto commitments are upheld
8- Ethically defensible (morally correct) the wishes and practices of all individuals and society are respected in decision-making, as well as those practices related to management of the environment and the protection of flora and fauna (e.g. mammals, seabirds, etc.); the actions of one generation do not impact adversely on following generations
9- Culturally inclusive local customs and accepted traditional practices are protected and respected even if such practices are considered ethically indefensible by those outside that culture (e.g. annual cetacean culls)
10- Effectively communicable all stakeholders are sufficiently informed, that decision-making and influence by all stakeholders is inclusive and ocean literacy is promoted

operationalisation, i.e. the Ecosystem-Based Approach (EBA) to Ecosystem-Based Management (EBM) and to the new term of Ecosystem-based Technical Measures (EBTM). It further discusses the weighting of the tenets and whether any tenets are missing from the holistic scheme.

Previous papers (Elliott, 2013; Borja and Elliott, 2019) have taken the view that all tenets are standalone, but not mutually exclusive, and are required for successful and sustainable marine management (Fig. 1). Fig. 1 also indicates that marine management is the result of overarching policies, whether by governments, international and global agencies, or industries and activity managers. Similarly, it is important to understand the data and information requirement. For example, the tenets 1–5 in Table 1 are quantitative and can be obtained as an amount or factually from government and other sources, whereas 6–10 are qualitative and can only be indicated as narratives, possibly based on stakeholder interviews. These differences are especially important when considering

policy instruments expressed in legislation, regulations, standards, or guidelines. Accordingly, within the holistic framework of the tenets, researchers and advisors must then use the precise wording of these laws, etc., to provide advice to marine managers (Borja et al., 2025). Therefore, as research scientists involved in policy implementation and advice, we see the need to frame these tenet concepts in the light of new research but especially against a science-policy interface background.

2. The ten-tenets as a continuum, nested and overlapping series

Recent discussions (in the international projects acknowledged below) have caused us to suggest that the tenets should be considered interlinked as a nested and overlapping continuum – i.e. a Venn diagram (Fig. 2). Although there are nine societal tenets, only one other relates to the natural structure and functioning (*Ecologically sustainable*), but this becomes all-encompassing given the imperative need to protect and maintain the natural system, both for its own intrinsic value and for the benefits to society (Borja et al., 2013). It is emphasised here that EBA, EBM, and EBTM are anthropocentric constructs and so we use rules which are required through policies, legislation, standards, certifications, guidelines etc... to manage socio-economic activities. The *Ecologically sustainable* tenet should occur independently of the policies, management, and technical measures implemented whereas the communication tenet particularly applies to all ten-tenets. In this anthropocentric system, the remaining eight then allow sustainably delivering the societal goods, desires and benefits without jeopardising that natural system.

The adverbs attached to each tenet indicate their implementation and the Venn diagram overlaps represent interactions between the tenets along a statutory policy, planning and regulatory timeline in a public policymaking cycle and within a social-ecological system (SES) (Smith et al., 2025). The Fig. 2 side-bar annotations shows that public policy cycle starts the policymaking, then moves on to plan and programme, and ultimately some form of a Programme of Measures is created through regulations, standards, or guidelines (a la Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD), Water Framework Directive (WFD)) (European Commission, 2008, 2000).

The continuum (Fig. 2) shows the progression from the EBA, to the EBM and then to the EBTM. Defining these, EBA is the overall approach behind marine management based on public (or even industrial) policies from the highest level (a top-down direction) or from societal wishes (a bottom-up direction). The term EBM then implies actions necessary for implementing EBA with a set of principles, regulations and associated methods for enacting those principles (Papadopoulou et al., 2025; Franco et al., submitted). This then needs to be further operationalised by instruments and tools (i.e. EBTM). The term EBA is used in many marine management policies and instruments but has been described as the Ecosystem-Based Approach to Management (Papadopoulou et al., 2025), thereby conflating two aspects (the EBA with EBM). Here, EBM and EBTM are then respectively summarised as the plans and programmes of management and their operational implementation.

The Fig. 2 illustrates a simple policy logic model. For example, *Socially desirable/tolerable* is the interface between *Culturally inclusive/Ethically defensible* and *Politically expedient/Legally permissible*; *Administratively achievable* is at the interface between *Politically expedient/Legally permissible* and *Technologically feasible/Economically viable*. This highlights the possibility of two bottlenecks where a single tenet is at one level in the sequence – the *Socially desirable/tolerable* and *Administratively achievable* tenets. Whatever is *Socially desirable or tolerable* is influence by the culture, ethics, and morals of the diverse communities in that society. That also implies that *Socially desirable* is the key factor of what would become *Politically expedient* and *Legally permissible* as public policies, i.e. the essence of marine policymaking. That which is *Administratively achievable* is more or less framed by what is *Politically expedient* and *Legally permissible*. This also implies that *Administratively achievable* is the key to what would be considered *Technologically feasible* and

Fig. 1. The Ten-tenets indicating those which are quantitative and numerical compared to those qualitative and narrative.

Economically viable. This is where Plans and programmes become implemented operationally by industry. Thus, *Socially desirable or tolerable* and *Administratively achievable* are the interfaces between EBA, EBM, EBTM. The three other areas are very much independent realms without the interfaces above (i.e. Culturally/Ethically, Politically/Legally, and Technologically/Economically). Finally, the flow of information and decisions for EBA, EBM, EBTM are required to ultimately ensure management is *Ecologically sustainable*.

3. Over-arching tenets – environment/ecology and communication

As achieving the *Ecologically sustainable* tenet envelopes the others, we emphasise that it is the most important for sustainability within the central social-ecological aim identified above. It is the overall aim in marine management as indicated in many national, European, regional and international agreements and legal instruments (Elliott et al., 2025; Cormier et al., 2022a). However, sustainability also implies that societal goods and benefits (including cultural and economic benefits) can be obtained after inputting human capital and natural assets (Elliott, 2023). For example, by maintaining the appropriate physico-chemical and ecological conditions which support fish populations which are

converted to yield via fisheries which can be exploited by human skills, energy, equipment, etc.

The other overarching tenet relates to communication and literacy, which are critical for those trying to understand, initiate, influence or respond to management solutions. It even should include lobbyists and those engaged in *direct action* outside the democratic process (for example the ‘Just Stop Oil’,² ‘Canary Islands against mass tourism’³ or ‘Extinction Rebellion’⁴ movements). The *Effectively communicable* tenet permeates throughout the continuum to enhance or at least reduce resistance to *Environmentally sustainable* actions. For example, this reflects the statutory consultation requirement in an Environmental Impact Assessment, i.e. ‘not just doing, but being seen to be doing’ (Elliott and Wither, 2024). It emphasises that the plethora of marine management and user organisations (Boyes and Elliott, 2015) need to talk to each other to overcome that management shall not be only on a sectoral basis (i.e. fishing, navigation, recreation, etc.) with resulting bias. As such, all management actions and responses should be effectively

² <https://juststopoil.org/>.

³ <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-europe-68865755>.

⁴ <https://rebellion.global/>.

Fig. 2. The ten-tenets presented as a Venn Diagram and Continuum – the *Effectively communicable* and *Ecologically sustainable* tenets are indicated as overarching tenets into which the remaining eight tenets are embedded; the dashed line encircles the narrative and qualitative tenets.

communicated.

Importantly, the role of influencers in the stakeholder typology (Newton and Elliott, 2016), such as academics, educators, NGOs, politicians, society at large, etc., relies on effective communication. These need to be sufficiently informed to know what is needed, what is being done, why is it being done and how information is being derived and used. In particular, the information and its accompanying data are communicated in the right place and time and in the right format (language, style, etc.) to allow feedback and advice in consultation (Borja et al., 2025; Cormier et al., 2015). Hence, this tenet identifies the importance of an informed public as well as all stakeholders and the central role of increasing ocean literacy.

4. Applying the ecosystem based approach (i.e. public policies)

Figs. 1 and 2 show the continuum of the tenets from those five in qualitative and narrative terms to those five which are quantitative and numerically described and defined. As EBA is an ‘approach’ then it can be qualitative and narrative and does not need to be quantitative and

have indicators although this also means it is difficult determining when it has been reached (Elliott et al., 2025). Hence, achieving the EBA relies on individual and/or collective behaviour in society which are governed by the ethical, moral and cultural ethos and which lead to policies.

The *Culturally inclusive* and *Ethically defensible/morally correct* aspects combine if everyone agrees what is *Morally correct* and the tenet *Socially tolerable or desirable* depends how *Culturally inclusive* and *Ethically defensible/Morally correct* is a given society; these aspects change continuously in time and space and culture is inseparable from ethics and morals and the wishes and tolerances of society. The societal tenet has always been given with alternative adverbs - to be desirable or tolerable. For example, society may desire coastal clean waters, but it usually tolerates pollution discharged into them either in the interests of economic growth or as a cheap way of dispersing, degrading and assimilating pollution. Similarly, society may desire clean waters or cheap nuclear power energy, but not a sewage treatment or power plant close to their homes (i.e. ‘not in my back yard’, NIMBY) (Devine-Wright, 2009). Despite this, societal wishes and tolerances should influence political judgement through democratic processes to create political

imperatives and possibly manifesto commitments (i.e. *Politically expedient*). In turn these are enacted through legal instruments and agreements.

Political expediency also relates to choices and behaviour but there may be cases where it counteracts the wishes and tolerances of parts of society. It either leads or follows what is *Socially desirable* when developing public policies that affects everyone in a society. What society considers desirable is by far influenced by the culture of the people and their communities. However, there is conflict if a head of state does not consider climate change to be a problem but the general population, despite the democratic process (or changing demography between election and office), thinks otherwise. This then reaches extreme lengths with *direct action* from groups (examples above) who feel their voice is not heard within democratic processes.

5. The continuum from EBA to EBM

In implementing the tenets, the challenge in marine management is to move from an approach (EBA) to management actions (EBM). Public policy and especially economics and public safety appear to mostly determine political expediency rather than ecosystem-based policies. Thus, what is *Legally permissible* should reflect the tenet *Socially desirable/tolerable* within the culture of law making. This may be influenced by elites and lobbyists once the political system is elected; although only democratic processes are considered here, direct action has always been used and may cause a separation between what is desired by a small group in society and yet tolerated by the large remainder. The policy then gives statutory administrative bodies a legal mandate to manage based on the current government priorities. They achieve regulation through technical measures such as technologies that are feasible and *Economically viable* which can be quantified; for example, building a waste-water treatment plant. Similarly, the legal and administrative structures and their success can be measured, quantified and analysed, e.g. the numbers of legal instruments and their administrative bodies (Boyes and Elliott, 2014, 2015; Elliott et al., 2025).

The political, administrative and legal aspects constitute formal governance especially at national and international levels, but non-statutory governance is also enacted by marine users and industries, commonly termed business administration (i.e. the process of an offshore wind power company *governing* their activities). In this way, governance, as setting priorities either publicly or privately, merges into management which may be regarded as operationalising the actions needed for that governance.

5.1. Role of administration and the links from politics and legislation

Public administration may be regarded as the central point which integrates the nine other Tenets through their plans and programmes. They largely communicate with the public and consult with stakeholders in processes they are mandated to 'manage'. These range from strategic, regional, or project impact assessments to marine planning of activities as well as marine conservation. However, they manage a process (i.e. the *raison d'être* of EBM) but they do not make the overall policy decisions (the *raison d'être* of EBA). They advise the political system which makes decisions according to its priorities and what the public and the stakeholder wants or at least will tolerate (i.e. the approach, EBA, and political expediency).

As the continuum indicates the interdependent links between the tenets and so hampers success if any one tenet is not fulfilled, as indicated the social and administrative tenets have the greatest potential to be bottlenecks. Regulators are mandated to produce an assessment, a plan or recommendation to decision makers according to the context and the scope (i.e. EBA) given to them. Hence, there is the need to determine what are the issues and try to consider and analyse them through individual dialogue or through group discussion with many stakeholders with their values, beliefs, desires and preoccupations. For

example, the UK stakeholder-led Marine Conservation Zone (aka MPA) project cascaded from a political desire, through policy and a legislative instrument (the Marine and Coastal Access Act) to a statutory body (English Nature) and then stakeholder panels for the design followed by the Marine Management Organisation for implementation (Lieberknecht and Jones, 2016).

An environmental manager must stick to the mandate and the timeframe provided (*Politically expedient*) and the prevailing adopted legislation (*Legally permissible*) in relation to inputs from all stakeholders (Cormier et al., 2015). However, *Legally permissible* depends on what is *Socially tolerable or desirable* when *Politically expedient* creates legislation. The mandate of statutory administrations depends on what is *Politically expedient* and *Legally permissible* when developing plans and programmes such as forcing industry to perform an environmental impact assessment or coordinating marine planning. Non-statutory (business) administrations include the developer and activity users in fully carrying out their activities (Elliott et al., 2025).

6. Applying Ecosystem-Based Management (EBM) (i.e. plans and programmes as response measures)

As indicated above, most of the public and their elected politicians have priorities which often are not linked to the natural ecosystem and perhaps more focussed on public safety, social conditions and economics. The public administration will always have to fulfil their governance mandate. For example, to ensure sewage treatment, the planning process will have to decide how best to achieve waste disposal which may take precedence over conservation and protected marine areas policies. The pressure of dealing with human waste thereby gives a hierarchy where managers must deal with the immediate problem and conservation and protection may come second to mitigation and prevention.

Achieving ecosystem sustainability requires practical technical (management) measures that can prevent and mitigate the pressures from activities and remediate their consequences. Management by statutory bodies then cascades into management by public and private developers. For example, politics decides on a cleaner environment, a law is enacted which prevents sewage discharges into the sea, then the Environmental Protection Agency issues a licence and polices public and private sewage discharge bodies, who build sufficient sewage treatment capacity to prevent being legally sanctioned and hence fulfil the original policy.

The political and legal aspects are thus implemented by public (statutory) administrative bodies who, together with the operators of activities, can then require EBTM based on the available technology and any economic imperatives. The legal and administrative aspects require to be horizontally integrated, across the main sectors of marine use (fisheries, navigation, recreation, etc.), and vertically integrated, from the local through national and regional to global and vice versa (Boyes and Elliott, 2014, 2015; Cormier et al., 2022a). Success in achieving these quantitative tenets can be measured within a planning system (Elliott et al., 2025).

7. Applying Ecosystem-Based Technical Measures (EBTM) (i.e. the operational implementation of response measures)

By definition, high level stakeholders are involved in creating the EBA which is then operationalised by EBM then using EBTM to achieve and maintain a functioning ecosystem and provide ecosystem services and societal goods and benefits (Elliott, 2023). When making decisions regarding technical measures, the feasibility of technology, the economic viability of an industry and the protection of the ecosystem follow the concept *as low as reasonably in practice* (ALARP) for risk reduction (Cormier et al., 2022b). For example, a dredging company will modify its activities or bring in mitigation measures such as a silt curtain to minimise the release of suspended sediment.

Public and private (business) administrators and managers and stakeholders select technical measures depending on what is *Technologically feasible* and *Economically viable* to create an *Ecologically sustainable* system. This is then achieved pragmatically as the net result of the interaction between the three and may follow the BATNEEC approach (Best Available Technology Not Entailing Excessive Cost) (Elliott and Wither, 2024).

Feedback and advice from scientists, technical experts and engineers is required to ensure sustainable and successful outcomes based on best available and *Legally defensible* evidence. Management questions usually focus on the anthropogenic causes and consequences to the environment (*Ecologically sustainable*), human health (*Socially desirable*) and economics (*Economically viable*). More importantly, questions are solved by the appropriate EBTM (*Ecologically sustainable*, *Technologically feasible*, and *Economically viable*) which are needed to reduce the risks to ALARP (Baybutt, 2014; Cormier et al., 2022b). However, risks cannot be eliminated due to scientific, management, or operational uncertainties (IEC/ISO, 2019). Recommendations inform a decision-maker about the potential causes and consequences of environmental damage and the technical measures that could be used to pursue environmental and societal objectives; for example, advisors influence the administrators issuing dredging licences which requires the dredging company to perform monitoring. Furthermore, feedback and advice are often qualitative (with caveats) as they reflect judgement and expertise even though they are based on best available evidence and extensive quantitative tools and expert judgement (Borja et al., 2025). It is axiomatic that data, models, and papers do not make decisions but are needed to support them.

Feedback, critical to effective communication, is used to understand the values, beliefs, cultures, desires, and preoccupations of stakeholders regarding the context and scope of the problem being addressed. Advisors comment on the feedback provided by stakeholders and the specific context and scope of the EBA-EBM-EBTM sequence. Scientific feedback is included with that from the other stakeholders, but it must be specifically framed within the question being asked and should be objective and independent of the values, beliefs, desires, and preoccupations of an individual scientist (and scientists as lobbyists should declare as such) (Gluckman, 2016; Rice, 2011; Rose and Parsons, 2015). The wording of policy instruments expressed in legislation, regulations, standards, or guidelines, cannot be changed by advisors and academia who must provide advice to answer the management question rather than pursue their own academic scientific question (what may be regarded as the ‘need-to-know’ rather than the ‘nice-to-know’). In applied science and engineering, new scientific research opportunities should be identified and pursued as long as they are framed within the policy and legal instruments (Cormier et al., 2022a, 2022b).

Feedback and advice from any source are always in relation to the recommendations within the context and the scope of the process and not the decision. As a matter of protocol, an influencer participant that wants to influence the decision is referred to the decision maker. This is because the regulator (the public administrator) does not have the authority to modify the context and the scope of the political decision-maker thereby keeping *Administratively achievable* separate from *Politically expedient*.

8. Discussion, weighting and concluding remarks

After more than a decade of use, it is concluded that the ten-tenets are appropriate for the continuum EBA-EBM-EBTM and without EBTM, EBM objectives are not achieved and EBA is merely wishful thinking (Cormier et al., 2013, 2015, 2018). However, internationally accepted guidance does give greater importance to adopting approaches, for example in relation to society and ethics, the ISO (2010). Despite this, while it would be difficult to write a uniform/accepted standard for EBA, instruments such as ISO 31000 (ISO, 2018) can lead to the EBTM or the so-called Programmes of Measures such as the EU MSFD

and WFD (Borja et al., 2010). The EBTM indirectly address social desires and political expedience. For example, the Programmes of Measures should both ensure that marine good environmental status is achieved, pollution is controlled and even oil spills are cleaned afterwards.

The Venn diagram (Fig. 2) shows the interaction during different steps of a management process. *Culturally inclusive* and *Ethically defensible* comprise and influence what is *Socially desirable/tolerable* at the start of the management process. The public scale of *Socially desirable/tolerable* mainly influences the policy policies that become *Politically expedient* as well as the legislation that becomes *Legally permissible*. Once the *Politically expedient* and the *Legally permissible* are established, it can take years to develop plans and programmes that are administratively achievable. Once *Administratively achievable*, any input control and spatial and temporal controls are implemented to manage how much, where and when human activities can take place and whether such controls are successful (Elliott et al., 2025). For example, in the case of the EU MSFD, output controls for ecosystem perturbations permitted for each individual pressures and all 11 descriptors (e.g. European Commission (2017) Table 2a: Anthropogenic pressures, and Table 2b. Uses and human activities) will always have to be *Technologically feasible* and *Economically viable* to achieve and maintain Good Environmental Status (e.g. European Commission (2008), Annex I).

Within the tenets framework and analysis here, it is necessary to question whether all tenets are weighted equally and/or whether they should be. In previous works, all tenets have been equally weighted on the basis that all are needed to be fulfilled to achieve successful and sustainable marine management. As indicated above, however, they are not mutually exclusive. Barnard and Elliott (2015) attempted to quantify the tenets and relate to indicators for each tenet; they used a radar plot to determine the degree of compliance within each tenet but working on the basis that all tenets are equally weighted and so the plots had to comparably scale the tenets. The difficulties of doing this reinforced the fact that some are quantitative/numerical and therefore can be assessed with SMART indicators (i.e. that these should be specific, measurable, achievable, realistic and time-dependent) and others qualitative/narrative which cannot (Cormier and Elliott, 2017).

It is now suggested here and in international agreements that the *Ecologically sustainable* tenet takes precedence in order to fulfil globally-recognised desires related to the ‘biodiversity, pollution and climate crises’ (Pettorelli et al., 2021). Hence, Fig. 2 shows this surrounding all other tenets. Similarly, all tenets require to be effectively communicated although it could be argued that successful and sustainable marine management could occur irrespective of whether all stakeholders are informed about it. Despite this, effective communication is necessary to link the science to policy and the policies to the people and vice versa (respectively top-down and bottom-up). It is necessary to get the funding and support for actions to create an informed and agreed management (Borja et al., 2025).

With regard to the other eight tenets, Fig. 2 suggests (as the size of the circles) they have the same weighting. This suggests that a proposed starting point may be as given below after giving importance to the

Table 2
A proposed weighting of the ten-tenets.

Number	Tenet	Weighting
1	Ecologically sustainable	26
2	Technologically feasible	8
3	Economically viable	8
4	Legally defensible	8
5	Administratively achievable	8
6	Socially tolerable/desirable	8
7	Politically expedient	8
8	Ethically defensible/morally correct	8
9	Culturally inclusive	8
10	Effectively communicable	10
Total		100

ecological and communication tenets (Table 2).

However, we acknowledge that they may be weighted differently depending on which stakeholders are involved and who is doing the assessment. For example, in any given society and community, however these are defined, there are many social desires based on the cultural fabric. Protecting cultural aspects is especially important and may be highly weighted in countries with large indigenous populations such as Australia, Canada or New Zealand, but less so in Europe where there are few and geographically very restricted indigenous groups (e.g. the Sámi in northern Scandinavia). However, contentious issues such as the cultural aspects of marine mammal harvesting (culling) by indigenous people may conflict with ethical concerns outside those particular societies, for example the Faroe Island long-finned pilot whale annual culls (the grindadráp) (Simmons, 2024). Each person or the society as a whole has values, beliefs, desires and preoccupations whenever they are faced with a decision to be made by themselves or someone else. Hence, the tenet must be tolerable or desirable. The scientific research is also influenced the cultural repercussions.

Elsewhere, the legal tenet may be paramount because of damaging ultimate legal sanctions. For example, companies being prosecuted for failing a licence or a member state, as in Europe, being placed in infraction proceedings for failing a Directive. Resorting to legal proceedings by or on a country, public or private body may suggest that management has failed (Elliott et al., 2025). Political expediency may take precedence for the head or executive of a government in ensuring that a manifesto on which they were elected is met. Governance may be pre-eminent as it includes, but not is exclusive to, policies and politics (i.e. EBA), and statutory administration and legislation (i.e. EBM) but is also taken as the means of ‘governing’ any entity and therefore, when operationalised, becomes synonymous with management.

In addition to this statutory governance, governance is a way of ‘governing’ all marine activities using economic and technical measures. Given the importance and desire/need for economic growth, the economics tenet may be paramount especially in neoliberal (i.e. free-market) doctrines; if there is insufficient funding to enact all the other tenets then successful and sustainable management will not be achieved. Similarly, if the equipment, techniques and technologies to manage and prevent (or restore from) the adverse effects of our activities and their pressures, are not available then that management cannot be achieved.

The remaining tenets relate to society and the higher basic human needs, the so-called Drivers such as providing food, health, employment and pleasure (Elliott et al., 2017). Both societal demands and desires may relate more to a local area and local affairs – for example, sewage on a local beach may concern local people more than climate change. Societal demands should permeate through political and local activities with society influencing the political process. The ethics and morals of damage to the seas, including effects (financial or otherwise) on future generations could also be given the highest weighting by certain stakeholders, especially those favouring direct action.

Therefore, although each stakeholder group may make a case for a particular tenet being paramount, we conclude from an EBA context that the only objective and independent weighting is as proposed in Table 2. Furthermore, in using the tenets over the past decade, in general they are regarded as comprehensive. However, recent discussions have questioned whether religion, equity and justice should also be added. Despite their importance in human societies and fulfilling the higher (ethereal) basic human needs, in the interests of not complicating the tenets even further, we consider that these are already embedded in the tenets *Ethically defensible (morally correct)*, *Culturally inclusive* and *Socially desirable/tolerable*. However, we note the recent suggestion that the well-used SMART approach to designing indicators and objectives (e.g. Cormier and Elliott, 2017) for determining environmental change is being extended to SMARTIE with the addition of inclusiveness and equity.

It is concluded that the ten-tenets concepts appear to stand up to wider use in marine management, but we emphasise that these are based

in a continuum. Assessing and employing these ten-tenets is central to marine risk management and spatial planning (Cormier and Kannen, 2019; Cormier et al., 2019). This includes the risk of human activities and their pressures adversely affecting ecology and society and the risk of not achieving the tenets. This centres around the fact that hazards can occur naturally or by human action, but they become risks when they adversely affect something valued by individuals or society. Therefore, management approaches and measures, embodied in the tenets, are required. As indicated here, two of the tenets are overarching and regarded as paramount but all tenets are required to be fulfilled to achieve successful and sustainable management.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Michael Elliott: Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Investigation, Supervision, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Roland Cormier:** Conceptualization, Investigation, Validation, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Ángel Borja:** Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Investigation, Validation, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests:

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Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

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